

Influencing Factors in Teaching Career Choices in Cambodia in Teacher Education Colleges: A Conceptual Framework

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Abstract

An education system should strive to attract qualified teachers and teacher candidates who have a high degree of professional commitment to meet the society requirements these days as well as, in the future, toward country development. The purpose of this study was to investigate the factors influencing the decision to teach career choices and aspirations among primary and lower secondary school teachers in Cambodia and student teachers at teacher education colleges (TECs). This study was synthesized from several previous studies, review papers, academic publications, public organization sources, instructional resources and empirical investigations. Four main factors, namely, the influence of others, including family, friends, teachers and mass media; motivational influences; sociocultural factors; and teaching as a fallback career, influence the decision to choose teaching as a career. The implications of the findings from the various sources have been discussed in this study. This study can help relevant people, as well as other researchers, to be aware of the influencing factors in career choice so that they can refine recruitment policies, increase their actions and efforts, and enter a preparation program for teaching careers in the Cambodian context.

Keywords: *student teachers, teaching career, teacher education college, influencing factors.*

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Introduction

Teaching is a noble profession and has helped shape many societies and nations. As explained by Richardson and Watt (2006), governments worldwide recognize that quality teachers and teaching are central to the development and maintenance of intelligent people. They also mentioned that working as a teacher may not be a profitable profession, but it has been regarded as the noblest mission, vocation and profession that contributes mainly to the nonmaterial satisfaction of individuals who are engaged in it. The ideology for someone to choose teaching as a career is based on working lighthouse image, their previous knowledge, self-perceptions in different areas related to the profession, and the aspirations of the profession.

The education system in Cambodia has undergone a remarkable transformation owing to considerable efforts by the Cambodian government and relevant stakeholders. In general, education has improved across the subsector. For example, there have been many efforts to improve the quality of teachers and school principals as well as their educational infrastructure. The Royal Government of Cambodia (RGC),

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through the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport (MoEYS), has introduced several projects, such as the Secondary Education Improvement Project and the General Education Improvement Project, to improve the general education subsector (Heng & Sol, 2022; Tao & Kao, 2023; Lan et al., 2024a; Lan et al., 2024b). In 2014, a major reform to the Grade 12 national examination was introduced to combat corruption and cheating during exams (Bredenberg, 2022; Sam et al., 2012 a; Sam et al., 2012b; Sam et al., 2013). In 2016, another reform to general education was undertaken: the introduction of a school improvement initiative known as the new generation school (NGS). This important initiative aims to create a new model of Cambodian public schools to improve the quality of general education (Bredenberg, 2022; Tieng et al., 2023).

Problem Statement

In the modern world, many people want to work in professional fields such as engineers, pilots or doctors to earn a large amount of money or to obtain a better career for their future. Teaching seems to be a less attractive profession because of low salaries and poor employment conditions (Kyriacou & Coulthard, 2000). Although education still competes with other types of careers, teaching careers are altruistically motivated in Cambodia (MoEYS, 2023).

Furthermore, according to MoEYS (2023), over the past decade (2013--2022), there has been significant progress in the development of educational infrastructure, student enrollment, and education access. For example, the number of kindergarten and general education schools increased from 14,852 in the 2013--2014 academic year to 18,830 in the 2022--2023 academic year. Additionally, the number of HEIs increased from 110 from 2013--2014 to 132 from 2021--2022. Moreover, the number of education staff also increased from 112,704 in 2013 to 125,597 in 2022. Therefore, this study examines the factors influencing the career decisions of teachers in Cambodia. The researchers are intrinsically motivated to start this study since they are seeking those factors that explain why people in Cambodia choose teaching as their career.

Figure 1. Increases in the Number of Schools, HEIs and Teachers

Purposes of the Study

This study investigates the factors that influence the career decisions of primary and lower secondary school teachers and student teachers from teacher education colleges. This study was also conducted to analyze the significant differences between each factor that influences the respondents' decision to choose teaching as a career as well as to understand the student teachers' perceptions of teaching career decisions from both teacher education institutions. Moreover, this research aims to provide useful insights into the factors that influence teaching career choice and to provide useful and relevant

information, which is required by the following sectors: administrations, parents, teachers, students and other researchers.

Research Method

This conceptual paper systematically examines and summarizes existing sources from some previous studies, review papers, academic publications, public organization sources, instructional resources and empirical investigations. By synthesizing those documents concerning the causes of teaching career choice, this study provides a conceptual framework that focuses on only four main factors influencing teaching career decisions. The reviewed documents are derived from sources between 2000 and 2023, ensuring that this paper covers reliable data about teaching career decisions in the Cambodian context.

Literature Review

Influence of Others on Teaching Career Decisions

Previous studies have shown that several sectors are related to the influence of others on career choices. For example, one study conducted in Ghana revealed that teachers do not significantly influence the career aspirations of students, while parents' influence is a major determinant of the career aspirations of students, and peers influence the career aspirations of male and female students differently. The influence of peers on the career aspirations of students does not vary on the basis of age or program of study (Owusu et al., 2022). However, in a study of 1249 secondary school students in Hong Kong (Lai et al., 2005), the influence of others included several sectors, such as the family, friends, teachers, and mass media. In one of several studies that reported on the career goals of secondary school students, Lai et al. (2005) reported that the influence of others had both a negative influence and a positive influence on the choice of teaching as a career.

Family influence on teaching career choices

Research on family influence has increased rapidly during the last few years, but the understanding of family influences on career choices remains limited. Many studies on family influence on career choice focus on individual parents' careers; for example, mothers or fathers influence children to generally take up a certain career as they do. This research revealed that family members, which include parents, siblings and extended family members, influence career decisions. The first interactions of a child with other people occur with his home's family members, including his parents, siblings and other relatives (Bollu-steve & Sanni, 2013). A child is influenced by a number of family-related factors, such as the marital relationship of the parents, the socioeconomic status of the family, the home atmosphere, whether parents are warm or hostile, the environmental condition, the occupational status of the parents and the number of siblings in the family (Bollu-steve & Sanni, 2013:92). Family dynamics, therefore, play a pivotal role in the career readiness of students. Several studies provide evidence that parental involvement influences high school students' career choices, for instance, in Romania (Marinas, Igret, Marinas & Prioteasa, 2016) in the Philippines (Aguado, Laguado & Deligero, 2015). These studies showed that parents influence the choice of career among high school students. A study conducted in Kenya revealed that when adolescents required information on topics such as career planning, they consulted their parents (Edwards & Quinter, 2012). Supportive parents are important for their children's career decision-making and for the success of their careers (Clutter, 2010). If an individual always observes his or her mother and admires her teaching skills, that may influence the pursuit of a career in education. Wright, Perrone-McGovern, Boo, & White (2014) reported that support from the most influential people is likely to have more direct influence on career decision-making self-efficacy than other contextual factors.

Kniveton (2004) reported that parents have much greater influence on students' career decisions than teachers do. The study indicated that young children begin to identify with their parent's occupation as soon as they can pronounce their job title. Peterson, Stivers, & Peters, as cited in Clutter (2010), indicated

that although adolescents begin to demonstrate their independence actively from their parents in their high school years, they are still very much dependent on their parents for their career development. In fact, parents tend to create the strongest impression of their children's career choices rather than any other group, such as counsellors, teachers or even friends (Bardick, Berns, Magnusson, & Witko, 2004). Additionally, Jungen (2008) noted that choosing a career is often a major change in a person's life, and this decision alone has the potential to open the door for having success or closing the door of opportunity. While often perceived to be an individual choice, the study suggested that a variety of influences, such as family, school, community, social and economic factors, are likely to manipulate one's final career decision. Among these factors, students report that parents have the greatest influence on which career they choose.

Friend influence on teaching career choices

According to Abdulla (2024), a senior career development specialist at the Qatar Career Development Center (QCDC) mentioned that friends and peers significantly influence individuals' lives, including their future career choices. Having friends who share the same interests and ambitions can influence a person's career choices, guiding them toward a specific professional way, as people generally feel comfortable and confident when they are surrounded by friends with similar interests. Peer influence also extends to expanding knowledge and learning opportunities. When individuals have friends with similar interests, they can always communicate and discuss things related to their shared interests. Abdulla's study was conducted in 2015 with 220 high school students in Qatar about the most influential factors in career decisions. The study revealed that friends were the factor with the most influence on others, as 180 students chose the same career path as their peers did. While some students were influenced by their peers and parents, others were influenced by different factors. However, friends were the most significant factor in these students' career decisions.

There are various ways in which peers can influence individuals' career choices. One of the major ways in which friends influence people is their ability to provide them with a sense of comfort and acceptance. People mostly find it easier to accompany their old friends and make new friends with them in the future. This, along with developing a sense of belonging to the group by following the group's preferences, is one of the main reasons why people choose to pursue careers that their peers are following as well (Rosenqvist, 2017). Others, who are confused about their future and do not have much exposure to what all they could pursue, tend to follow the general trend they see among their peers (Rosenqvist, 2017). In addition, friends are often compared to, academically, the individuals making the decision.

According to Salvy, Haye, Bowker, & Hermans (2012), friends are great sources of motivation to each other. Lifelong friendships are made at schools, and friends are known to stand up for one another, sometimes even more than siblings. They help each other with school work and become mentors to each other in their personal lives (Salvy et al., 2012). Additionally, Ogotu, Odera & Maragia (2017) examined the influence of friends on students' career decision making. They reported that friend influence had a positive relationship with career choice. Naz, Saeed, Khan, Khan, & Sheikh (2014) explored the nature, level and extent of peer and friend influence in the career decision process of an individual. The study revealed that even though families primarily prepare and transform children's behavior in many ways, friend influence is a resource for developing career opportunities and decision making among youth.

Teacher influence on teaching career choices

According to Tira Nur Fitria (2023), teachers have the ability to inspire and motivate students. They can spark a love of learning, encourage students to try new things and push them to reach their full potential. Teachers, through their enthusiasm and dedication, can instill a love for a subject or a specific field, which can have a significant effect on a student's career choices.

Teachers are creatures who are given the mandate to educate humans to become human beings who have good character, have character, and are knowledgeable (Normawati et al., 2019). Teachers are professional educators with the main tasks of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing, and evaluating students (Pianda, 2018). The teacher's role is very important in the teaching and learning

process, as well as in advancing the world of education (Wijaya, 2018). Teachers who carry out their duties professionally will be able to provide great and dignified educational output (Octavia, 2019). Becoming a teacher usually begins with interest. Interest in the teaching profession is a person's willingness or desire to pursue the teaching profession, where the teaching profession has a professional role and competence and requires special skills as a teacher. Elements of interest in becoming a teacher can start from studying at the faculty of teacher training and education, seeking knowledge and information about the teaching profession, feelings of pleasure and interest in the teaching profession, and the willingness and desire to become a teacher.

Khan, Murtaza & Shafa (2012) investigated the role of teachers in career counseling in high schools in Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan. The findings showed that teachers voluntarily act as students' informal counsellors who guide them in their subject choices and career paths. Moreover, they indicated that students view their teachers as role models and attach high value to their advice and guidance related to career choice. Shumba and Naong (2012) determined the factors influencing career choice and aspirations among students in South Africa. They reported that the family is the ability of the student to identify his or her preferred career choice and that teachers are the main factors that influence the students' career choices and aspirations.

Influence of mass media on teaching career choices

Media and communication technology have affected modern life by influencing one's perception of the world and interfering with personal interactions with individuals and society (Hoag & Grant, 2017). Research has shown that mass media influences the career selection process by shaping personal decisions since it contributes to character development, language and habit formation (Noshina, Mian, Irfaan & Rao, 2014; Kazi & Akhlaq, 2017). Studies conducted in countries such as the United States of America, Australia and Nigeria have indicated that media such as TV, radio, internet, newspapers and social media sites have contributed to students' choices of careers in librarianship and journalism (Dana, 2017; Busayo, 2017). Further studies by Kazi and Akhlaq (2017) and Adedeji, Ojelabi, Lekan and Adefarati (2017) insist that high school students' career choices are influenced by notable personalities in certain professions, as seen on television, heard on radios and read on printed media.

Proposition 1: The influence of others, such as family, friends, teachers and mass media, has a positive influence on teaching career decisions.

Motivational Factors in Teaching Career Decisions

Motivational factors are most frequently found when searching for the decision to choose a teaching career, as they are divided into altruistic, intrinsic, and extrinsic motivations. While there is some overlap between these types of motivations, especially between altruistic and intrinsic motivation, these terms are broadly used in the literature. Altruistic behavior is described as human actions with no apparent benefits for the person who performs them but who benefits other individuals, shows a generous love of others, desires their discovery of happiness and expects nothing in return (Altruism/Psychology Today, n.d.). Some examples related to motivation for choosing teaching include things such as a desire to work with children and adolescents, to make a social contribution, or to make a difference. Intrinsic motivation consists of engaging in a behavior because it is personally rewarding, performing an action for the pleasure it conveys, and it is for internal reward, not for some external reward. Intrinsic motivation defines the work itself as its reward and arises from within the individual because the work is naturally satisfying, they enjoy an activity, or they see it as an opportunity to discover, learn and update their possibilities (Griggs, 2017). Some examples related to motivation for choosing teaching include enjoying the work of teaching, compatibility with other interests and activities, compatibility with family life, and self-education. Extrinsic motivation arises from outside an individual and happens when they are moved to engage in an activity to earn a reward or evade penalty; that is, a person behaves in a specific way, not because of mere enjoyment or satisfaction but rather to obtain a payment or avoid an unpleasant consequence (Griggs, 2017). Some examples of extrinsic motivation include money, fame, grades, and admiration. People who are extrinsically motivated continue to perform an action although they do not

see the task rewarding. Another example related to this kind of motivation for teaching is having job security.

Moreover, Nesje et al. (2018) confirmed a Norwegian translation of the Factors Influencing Teaching Career Choice (FIT-Choice) scale and reported that the factors that Norwegian future teachers most strongly agreed with were intrinsic motivation, shaping the future of children or adolescents, perceived teaching ability, making social contributions, and ensuring job security. Lin et al. (2012) examined similar and differing initial motivations to teach between 257 U.S. and 542 Chinese preservice teachers via the FIT-Choice scale. The highest-rated motivations, which are common to both the U.S. and Chinese samples, were within social utility values (“make social contributions” and “shape the future of children or adolescents”). Similarly, the lowest mean rating for both groups was chosen for teaching as a “fallback” career, followed by socialization influences such as people who had encouraged them to embark upon a teaching career. Goller et al. (2019) used the FIT-Choice scale to discover undergraduate students’ motivations in Finland for choosing teaching as a career in comparison to student teachers in Germany. Compared with Finnish students, German students tended to choose their careers in more cases because they felt that their teaching abilities were high, judged the job as having high personal utility value, including strong job security and time for family, and were convinced by other people who the teaching career choice would be a good idea. Even though most students in both samples noted that they did not choose teaching as a fallback career, the German students scored significantly higher on this factor than did the Finnish students.

Proposition 2: Motivational factors such as altruistic, intrinsic, and extrinsic motivations have a positive influence on teaching career decisions.

Teaching as a Fallback Career in the Teaching Career Decision

Australian research conducted with 1653 preservice teachers from three universities in Australia revealed that teaching is not typically considered a fallback career, chosen only because other options were not available or did not work out (Richardson & Watt, 2006; Watt & Richardson, 2007). However, some evidence suggests that teaching is a fallback career for some students who are aspiring to other careers. For example, Australian research involving more than 6000 primary and secondary school students shows that teaching is considered a second option by some students who feel that their first choice of career may be out of reach (Gore et al., forthcoming). Internationally, research has also indicated that teaching may be considered if other options do not work out (Akar, 2012; Dastidar & Sikdar, 2015; Gu & Lai, 2012; Klassen et al., 2011; Lawver & Torres, 2011; Topkaya & Uztosun, 2012). Recent research has indicated that teaching as a fallback career is not necessarily negative. Menzies et al. (2015) reported that both “accidental entry” and “getting attracted to teaching” (p.7) are important reasons for entering the teaching profession, whereas Wong et al. (2014) reported that teaching as a fallback career could be positive when it was seen as a reasonable career choice and connected with intrinsic and altruistic motivation.

Proposition 3: Teaching as a fallback career has a positive influence on teaching career decisions.

Sociocultural Factors Affecting Teaching Career Decisions

Research within the last decade that has focused on the sociocultural influences surrounding the choice to enter teaching as a career has been limited. Much of the research pointing to this type of influence is international in nature and provides a point of comparison to influence the choice of teaching in Western countries. For example, a Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) may allow students’ direct entry into university. As such, preservice teachers in Nigeria indicated that they had taken a teaching course to increase their chances of being admitted to the university (Ejeh, 2005). In China and Hong Kong, negative images of teachers, including the reported low status of teachers, discouraged Chinese students from choosing teaching as a career, despite teaching being viewed more favorably in Chinese society more generally (Gao & Trent, 2009; Lai et al., 2005), whereas in Oman, religion and social expectations have a strong role in influencing Omani preservice teachers (Klassen et al., 2011). Furthermore, research

with African-American males in the United States has demonstrated how cultural understanding can influence students to not choose a career in teaching. These students identified three key reasons for not choosing teaching: (1) holding negative perceptions of teachers and teaching; (2) viewing schools as oppressive institutions where African–American males are stigmatized, labeled, and devalued; and (3) seeing teaching as “selling out” (p. 409), as it is believed that the curriculum represents black people inaccurately and unfairly (Graham & Erwin, 2011; Chork et al., 2024).

In Malaysia, cultural beliefs play a main role “in constructing favorable conditions in teaching and facilitating a positive image of the teaching career” (Azman, 2012), whereas English language (ELT) teachers in Turkey indicate that social influences, religious purposes, significant others and gender roles are key sociocultural influences on the choice of teaching as a career (Sali, 2013). Further research with 974 preservice teachers from Turkey illustrated how participant motivations and perceptions of teaching as a career were shaped by the sociocultural context of Turkish society (Akar, 2012), which included teaching as a suitable job for women and identifying teaching as a low-status profession. In one of several studies that focused on ethnic background as an influence on teaching career choice, Butt et al. (2010) undertook focus groups and qualitative interviews with 18 British South Asian women. The findings revealed that intrinsic motivations to teach, including job satisfaction, a sense of achievement, love for the subject and enjoyment of working with children, were also influential. Additionally, the influence on teaching career choice for British South Asian women was the flexibility offered by a teaching career and its perceived fit with both present and future family needs and the acceptability of teaching as a career with respect to its status in the community. Furthermore, the authors also noted responses from participants that suggested that their presence in schools as role models for their ethnic group was crucial, even though there was also acknowledgment that this could add more pressure (Butt et al., 2010).

In Australia, social influences were found to be less important than other factors, including intrinsic and altruistic motivation (Watt & Richardson, 2007). However, one qualitative study with Indigenous Australian people noted that “emotional capital” influences the choice of a teaching career (Santoro, 2010). The findings suggest that the mothers of indigenous students have an important influence on the choice of their children to enter a teaching career. Teaching in this context can be understood to represent good chances for “upward class mobility” and opportunities for social change to Indigenous people more generally (Santoro, 2010; Hoerng et al., 2024). Furthermore, Gore et al. (forthcoming) reported that indigenous primary and high school students are 1.6 times more likely to express an interest in teaching as a career than nonindigenous students are over and above the influence of other demographic factors.

Proposition 4: Sociocultural factors have a positive influence on teaching career decisions.

Proposed Research Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework Model

Conclusion

This research aimed to explore the major variables influencing the teaching career decisions of primary and lower secondary school teachers in Cambodia and fourth-year student teachers at Teacher Education College. A thorough analysis of research and theoretical frameworks led to the identification of various predictor variables, demonstrating the intricate interaction between independent and predictive variables influencing teachers' and student teachers' career choices.

In conclusion, the main factor influencing teaching career decisions is the influence of others, such as other teachers, friends, family and mass media. Another factor is the motivational factor, which includes altruistic, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The third factor is teaching as a fallback career, and teaching may be considered if other options do not work out. The fourth factor is the sociocultural factor, which includes the status of teachers, religion, social expectations, gender roles, and cultural understanding.

Researchers would intend to provide useful insights into the factors that influence teachers' choice of teaching as a career. The useful and relevant information from this study would benefit the following sectors:

-Administration: This study could help policymakers and school leaders in the Cambodian educational system refine recruitment policies and practices for teaching careers.

-Parents: This study will inform parents about their children's career choices.

-Teachers: The knowledge gained from such studies could be used to increase the actions and efforts to recruit students with a higher academic and social profile for the teaching career.

-Students: This study could lead students to enter a preparation program for their teaching careers, and some actions could be taken to encourage more academically excellent students to pursue their teaching careers.

-Researchers: This study can help future researchers consider other factors that might affect students' preferences for certain careers.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that no conflicts of interest exist.

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